

Voltammetric Studies on some Substituted-3-cyano-1,5-diphenylformazans in Nonaqueous Medium

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The different substituted-formazans (1a-k) are electrochemically studied in benzonitrile with 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte using DC and cyclic voltammetry. They are oxidised in a single irreversible two-electron process to the corresponding tetrazole cation. The reduction occurs in one irreversible two-electron or two irreversible one-electron waves according to the nature of the substituent, forming the dianion.

THE increasing interest in the chemistry of formazans is due their biological activities¹⁻⁵. Although formazans have been extensively studied⁶ little has been reported about their electrochemical behaviour. Previously, we investigated the redox characteristic of some substituted-3-cyano-1,5-diphenylformazans in ethanol/buffer media using the voltammetric technique. In the present work the following substituted-formazans are investigated in proton-free benzonitrile using the DC and cyclic voltammetry.

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| 1a, R = C ₆ H ₅ | 1f, R = C ₆ H ₄ Cl-p |
| 1b, R = C ₆ H ₄ OH ₂ -p | 1g, R = C ₆ H ₄ Cl-o |
| 1c, R = C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ -o | 1h, R = C ₆ H ₄ Br-p |
| 1d, R = C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ -p | 1i, R = C ₆ H ₄ Br-o |
| 1e, R = C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ -o | 1j, R = C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -p |
| | 1k, R = C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -o |

Experimental

Benzonitrile (BN) (Riedel, A.G.) was purified under reduced pressure by distillation from ortho-phosphoric acid followed by several distillations from phosphorous pentoxide (several times) and a finally from potassium metal.

The supporting electrolyte, tetra-n-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) (Fluka, A.G.) was crystallised several times from ethanol/water (9 : 1, v/v) and dried under reduced pressure before use.

Voltammetry: The voltammetric measurements were carried out using the following apparatus : VSG 72 voltage scan generator, PCA 72C Bank electronic potential control amplifier, Metrawatt Servogor xy-recorder and Hartmann-Braun T 2201 digital multimeter. The rotating platinum disc electrode was mounted to a Metrohm rotating motor (750 r/min).

The working electrode was a rotating platinum disc electrode (RDE), while the auxiliary a platinum wire immersed in the same electrolyte in a special jacket. All the potentials were measured against Ag/AgCl (BN) as reference electrode. The potential of the electrode was calibrated against the potential of the redox system cobaltocinium/cobaltocen (-743 mV) in benzonitrile⁷.

3-Cyano-1,5-diarylformazans (1a-g): The compound were prepared as previously reported for 3-cyano-1,5-diarylformazans⁸. Thus, substituted-anilines (0.1 mol) were diazotised and coupled with cyanoacetic acid (0.1 mol) dissolved in excess sodium carbonate solution. The reaction mixture was then acidified with cold dilute HCl till effervescence ceased, and warmed on a water-bath for 30 min. The 3-cyano-1,5-diarylformazans (1a-g) were filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

Results and Discussion

The substituted-3-cyano-1,5-diphenylformazans were studied using different voltammetric techniques including the direct current (DC) and cyclic

Fig. 1. DC-voltammogram of 1a in BN.

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TABLE I—DC-VOLTAMMETRY DATA OF DIFFERENT SUBSTITUTED-FORMMAZANS IN BENZONITRILE

Compd. no.	Process	$E_{1/2}$ mV	S^*	$E_{1/2} - E_{1/2}$	$E_{1/2}(O_1)/E_{1/2}(R_1)$	$\log K^{**}$	α
1a	O ₁	1 447	81	85	2 090	35.4	—
	R ₁	-649	121	11.5			
1b	O ₁	1 190	107	115	2 003	33.9	-0.97
	R ₁	-873	105	1.05			
1c	O ₁	1 457	110	115	2 188	37.0	—
	R ₁	-656	101	100			
1d	O ₁	1 457	110	115	2 113	35.8	-0.17
	R ₁	-656	101	100			
1e	O ₁	1 525	92	95	2 096	35.5	—
	R ₁	-571	87	85			
1f	O ₁	191	187	160	1 562	26.4	0.98
	R ₁	-354	127	120			
	R ₂	-854	109	100			
	R ₃	-1 544	97	80			
1g	O ₁	2 036	158	135	2 225	37.7	—
	R ₁	-189	113	100			
	R ₂	-729	181	140			
	R ₃	-1 454	125	180			
1h	O ₁	1 846	80	90	2 105	35.6	0.98
	R ₁	-259	83	150			
	R ₂	-909	111	100			
	R ₃	-1 454	192	210			
1i	O ₁	1 776	70	80	2 020	34.2	—
	R ₁	-244	118	115			
	R ₂	-754	102	100			
	R ₃	-1 329	96	100			
1j	O ₁	2 181	108	30	2 915	49.4	0.79
	R ₁	-000	70	60			
	R ₂	-734	154	120			
1k	O ₁	1 866	273	160	1 867	31.6	—
	R ₁	-001	93	160			
	R ₂	-1 144	272	300			

* $S = dE/d \log (i_a - i)$.

** K = Semiquinone formation constant.

Fig. 2. DC-voltammogram of compound 1f in BN.

voltammetry (CV). To obtain the number of electrons participating in each electrochemical process, the controlled potential coulometry was used. All measurements were carried out in proton-free benzonitrile with 0.1 M TBAP as supporting electrolyte under purified nitrogen atmosphere. The results are summarised in Table 1. Figs. 1 and 2 represent the typical DC-voltammograms while Figs. 3 and 4 the corresponding cyclic voltammograms of **1a** and **1f**, respectively. Table 1 and Figs. 1 and 3 reveal that compounds **1a**–**e** behave identically in both oxidation and reduction process. They were oxidised in a single irreversible two-electron wave. This apparent irreversibility is due to the fact that electron-transfer process is coupled with a followup chemical reaction (EC-mechanism) forming an electrochemically active form of these compounds which can be reduced in the reverse cycle (Fig. 3) at the potential range 50–400 mV according to the nature of the substituent in each compound. The reduction of these compounds occur also in one irreversible two-electron transfer process following the same mechanism as oxidation.

The chloro- or bromo-substituted compounds (**1f**–**i**) where the halogen atom is in the *ortho*- or

Fig. 8. Cyclic voltammogram of compound **1a** in BN : (a) oxidation and (b) reduction, scan rate = 100 mV s⁻¹.

para-position, are oxidised similarly to the above mentioned compounds but the reduction mode is different. They are reduced in well defined three irreversible one-electron transfer processes. The nitro-substituted derivatives (**1j**, **k**) are oxidised and reduced in the same manner as **1a**–**e** with the addition of the characteristic reduction wave of the nitro group which appear at relatively high negative potential.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of compound **1f** in BN : (a) oxidation and (b) reduction, scan rate = 100 mV s⁻¹.

Some attempts were made to study the electrochemical redox mechanism of different substituted 1,3,5-triphenylformazans^{9,10}, but very few attempts were made to find new voltammetric studies including the cyclic voltammetry on RDE electrode in nonaqueous medium, which is the aim of the present work.

The redox behaviour of formazan–tetrazolium salt system in acetonitrile using cyclic voltammetry and coulometry was studied by Tabakovic *et al.*¹¹. The authors concluded that the mechanism of intramolecular oxidative cyclisation of 1,3,5-triphenylformazan to 1,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium perchlorate involves cyclisation of the initial radical-cation and deprotonation as the rate-determining step. The two-electron oxidation product (1,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium perchlorate) is formed through oxidation of the parent 1,3,5-triphenylformazan to a radical-cation and then cyclised. The deprotonation of this cyclic radical-cation leads to the tetrazolium radical, which is the rate-determining step. It is difficult to decide whether the second electron is transferred through direct electron transfer or through solution electron transfer. The feasibility of the solution electron transfer is supported by Maender and Russel¹² who found by means of esr spectra that a mixture of formazan and tetrazolium salt gives rise to a paramagnetic product.

In the present work, all the compounds were oxidised in a single two-electron process leading to the formation of the corresponding di-cation. This electrochemical process is followed by the

splitting of one proton forming the mono-cation. The removal of proton can also be accompanied by ring closure forming the corresponding tetrazole cation. The mechanism is represented in Scheme 1.

The tetrazole cation can be stabilised through its combination with the perchlorate anion from the supporting electrolyte forming the tetrazolium perchlorate which can be reduced to the tetrazole as confirmed by the appearance of a reduction peak in the reverse cycle of the oxidation cyclic voltammogram.

The azo moiety in the investigated formazans is the center responsible for the reduction; it accepts the two electrons in one-step forming the corresponding di-anion which undergoes a fast chemical reaction with the solvent. Sadler and Bard¹³ and Boto and Thomas¹⁴ reported that in the reduction of some azo compounds the di-anion formed undergoes deprotonation with the solvent, through which the di-anion accepts one proton from the solvent to form the monoprotonated-dianion. In our case, the chemical reaction can be followed in the same manner. The di-anion reacts with the solvent forming the monoprotonated-dianion (or mono-anion) through the acceptance of one proton only. It can also accept two protons in one-step forming the corresponding hydrazono-derivatives.

The presence of two halogen atoms in the *ortho*- or *para*-position of the two phenyl groups (compound 1) will stabilise the formed mono-anion. The reduction of these compounds occurs in three one-electron processes. Due to this stabilisation effect, the two-electron wave splits into two one-electron waves leading to the formation of the radical-anion and the di-anion, respectively. This di-anion can be protonated through its reaction with the solvent as mentioned above. The third wave, which occurs at a relatively high negative potential corresponds to the reduction of the cyano group. The reduction mechanism is illustrated in Scheme 2.

Additional support for the above proposed electro-oxidation and -reduction schemes was found to be of importance. Thus, it appeared mandatory to study the effect of substituent on the reaction site of these molecules. The most reliable $E_{1/2}$ values have been correlated to Hammett constants¹⁵.

Scheme 2

Representative $E_{1/2}$ - σ plots are illustrated in Fig. 5 which reveal good linearity.

Fig. 5. Dependence of half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) of the *para*-substituted-formazans on the Hammett constant σ .

References

- V. S. MISRA, S. DHAR and B. L. CHOWDHARY, *Pharmazie*, 1978, 33, 790.
- D. D. MUKHERJEE, S. K. SHUKLA and B. L. CHOWDHARY, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1981, 314, 991.

3. D. D. MUKERJEE and S. K. SHUKLA, *Bolvn Bobas*, 1981, **9**, 521.
4. D. PALUT and Z. ECKSTEIN, *Bull. Acad. Pol. Sci., Ser. Sci. Chm.*, 1964, **12**, 41.
5. Z. R. BULKINA, L. S. PUPKO, E. F. GARLBENKO, M. N. DANCHENKO and P. S. PEL'KIS, *Ves. Aktiv. Veshchestva*, 1964, **2**, 91 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, **73**, 12657).
6. W. D. HOOPER, *Rev. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **19**, 221.
7. W. SUMMERMANN, Ph.D. Thesis, Freiburg University, 1970.
8. H. WESSBACK, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1903, **67**, 395.
9. M. VARGEK, GY. FARSANG and S. BALOGH, *Rolando Eotvos Nominatove, Sect. Chm.*, 1979, **15**, 191.
10. L. LASZLO, GY. FARSANG and B. SANDOR, *Acta Chm. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1975, **86**, 205.
11. I. TABAKOVIC, M. TRKOVNIK and Z. GRUJIC, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1979, 166.
12. O. W. MAENDER and G. A. RUSSEL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 442.
13. J. L. SADLER and A. J. BARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1979.
14. K. G. BORO and F. G. THOMAS, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, **24**, 975, 1973, **26**, 1251.
15. H. H. JEFFE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, **9**, 53.